

Enhanced superconductivity in Se-doped $\text{EuSr}_2\text{Bi}_2\text{S}_4\text{F}_4$ and $\text{Eu}_2\text{SrBi}_2\text{S}_4\text{F}_4$ under hydrostatic pressure

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Abstract:

The recently known BiS_2 layer containing superconductors has gained considerable attention. After the discovery of superconductivity in layered $\text{Bi}_4\text{O}_4\text{S}_3$ compounds has a tremendous amount of work on comes on BiS_2 -based systems has been carried out in the past six years. Here, the modification of superconductivity in the parent compound could be of great importance in studying both mechanism of superconductivity and exploration of new SC compounds at ambient and high-pressure conditions. Recently, we reported the induce superconductivity in $\text{EuSr}_2\text{Bi}_2\text{S}_4\text{F}_4$ by Se substitution at the S site (isovalent substitution) with T_c of ~ 2.9 K in $\text{EuSr}_2\text{Bi}_2\text{S}_2\text{Se}_2\text{F}_4$. The other compound, $\text{Eu}_2\text{SrBi}_2\text{S}_4\text{F}_4$, shows a significant enhancement of T_c . In Se-substituted $\text{Eu}_2\text{SrBi}_2\text{S}_{4-x}\text{Se}_x\text{F}_4$. At the same time, superconducting T_c of ~ 2.6 K for $x = 1.5$ and T_c of ~ 2.8 K for $x = 2$, whereas T_c of ~ 0.4 K in the Se-free sample. The enhancement of superconductivity in an important effect associated with Se substitution is that it gives rise to remarkable changes in the Eu valence. Further, here we report a systematic investigation of Se substituted in $\text{Eu}_2\text{SrBi}_2\text{S}_{4-x}\text{Se}_x\text{F}_4$ and $\text{EuSr}_2\text{Bi}_2\text{S}_{4-x}\text{Se}_x\text{F}_4$ ($x=1.5$ and 2) by electrical resistivity and magnetic susceptibility measurements under various applied pressures ranging from 0 to 3 GPa. Surprisingly, on applying external pressure we observe enhanced superconductivity in all the materials. Particularly, Highest T_c observed in $\text{EuSr}_2\text{Bi}_2\text{S}_2\text{Se}_2\text{F}_4$ compound at ~ 8 K (3 GPa) with 1.68 K/GPa. The field dependent upper critical field (H_{c2}) and thermal activation energy (U_0) was calculated using Werthamer–Helfand–Hohenberg (WHH) equation. The thermal activation energy of charge carriers could be determined from the thermal activation formula. The important essential properties of all the compounds are analyzed with application magnetic field and high pressure.

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